

Chemical Examination of *Christisonia bicolor* Gardn.*

A. B. Sen and S. P. Singh

The isolation of a rare carotenoid, azafrin, from the ether extract of the dried rhizomes of *C. bicolor* Gardn. has already been reported¹.

The rhizomes after extraction with ether were next percolated several times with rectified spirit and the percolates concentrated under reduced pressure below 50° to a thick syrup. The concentrate on keeping in a refrigerator for 7 days deposited a crystalline material. This was filtered, washed with ethanol (yield 0.8% on weight of dried rhizomes) and repeatedly crystallised from dilute methanol to provide colorless, silky needles, m.p. 166°. (Found: C, 39.42; H, 7.36. Calc. for C₆H₁₄O₆: C, 39.56; H, 7.69%).

The substance is readily soluble in water and insoluble in acetone. Its aqueous solution is sweet in taste, neutral to litmus, and negative to ferric chloride reaction. It did not reduce Fehling's solution as such or after heating with dilute acid. It did not depress the m.p. of an authentic sample of *D*-mannitol.

Hexa-acetylmannitol was prepared in the usual manner by heating the preceding compound with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate; m.p. 121°. (Found: C, 49.82; H, 6.21. Calc. for C₁₈H₂₆O₁₂: C, 49.77; H, 5.99%). The mixed m.p. of the product, when admixed with an authentic sample of hexa-acetylmannitol, remained undepressed.

The filtrate, after removal of mannitol, was completely freed of the solvent and the residue was taken in water. The clear aqueous solution was exhaustively extracted with butanol. The butanol extract was washed with a little water and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The residue gave positive tests for glycosides. It has not yet been possible to crystallise the glycoside.

The amorphous glycoside material was hydrolysed with 2% H₂SO₄ to afford a sugar, identified as glucose by paper chromatography, an ether-soluble aglycone fraction, and a dark, amorphous, ether-insoluble product.

The ether-soluble fraction could be divided into an alkali-soluble portion, yielding a crystalline acid, m.p. 199°, and a neutral portion. The latter is a yellow liquid, b.p. 118-119°/10⁻³ mm. It gave a dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 218° (decomp.), which was found to be homogeneous by thin layer chromatography on kieselgel G.

Further work on the structure of the acid and of the liquid ketone is in progress.

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY, LUCKNOW.

Received January 7, 1964.

1. Singh, *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 925.

*After publication of our first paper on the subject¹, Rajagopalan and Sheshadri have reported the isolation of azafrin and *D*-mannitol from *Alectra parasitica* (*Curr. Sci.*, 1964, 33, 174). Like *C. bicolor*, *A. parasitica* is a parasite on *Vitex negundo* and is known in Hindi as nirgundi. Since both the plants were also collected from the same area, Chitrakut in Banda district of U.P., it is highly probable that they are the same. This requires botanical confirmation.